

ON FAST HADAMARD TRANSFORMS OF WILLIAMSON TYPE

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ABSTRACT

The Hadamard transform of Sylvester's type, which is also known as the Walsh-Hadamard transform, is widely used in signal processing and communication. Note that the Walsh-Hadamard transform operates only with vectors whose length N is a power of 2. If N is not a power of two, then in order to compute the Walsh-Hadamard spectrum of the vector one has to either discard components or pad zeros up to the next power of two. In the first case we have an information loss and in the second case extra computations are needed. Thus, construction of fast Hadamard transforms of different orders is important problem. In this paper we develop fast Hadamard transforms based on special classes of Hadamard matrices, namely, the Williamson type Hadamard matrices.

1 Introduction

More than a hundred years ago, in 1893, Jack Hadamard [1] has proved that if $A = (a_{i,j})_{i,j=0}^{n-1}$ is an arbitrary real matrix of order n with entries $a_{i,j}$, with $-1 \leq a_{i,j} \leq +1$, then

$$|\det A|^2 \leq \prod_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n a_{i,j}^2,$$

where the equality is achieved when A is an orthogonal matrix, and for $a_{i,j} = \pm 1$ the determinant is getting maximal absolute value.

A (± 1) -matrix A of order n satisfying conditions

$$A^T A = A A^T = nI_n,$$

where T stands for transposition and I_n is the identity matrix of order n , is called a Hadamard matrix.

First class of Hadamard matrices was constructed by Sylvester in 1867 [2]. Sylvester's construction has the following form:

$$H_{2^k} = \begin{pmatrix} H_{2^{k-1}} & H_{2^{k-1}} \\ H_{2^{k-1}} & -H_{2^{k-1}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, \quad (1)$$

where $H_1 = (1)$.

Originally matrix of the form (1) was called the Sylvester's type Hadamard matrix [3, 4, 5], but nowadays is better known as the Walsh-Hadamard transform matrix.

This paper is devoted to development of fast Hadamard transforms based on the Williamson type Hadamard matrices.

2 Skew Symmetric Hadamard Matrices of Williamson Type

A Hadamard matrix H_{4n} of order $4n$ of the following form $H_{4n} = I_{4n} + S_{4n}$, where $S_{4n}^T = -S_{4n}$ is called a *skew symmetric Hadamard matrix* [4].

Let A, B, C, D be cyclic (± 1) -matrices of order n , satisfying the conditions

$$\begin{aligned} A &= I_n + A_1, \quad A_1^T = -A_1, \quad B^T = B, \\ C^T &= C, \quad D^T = D, \\ AA^T + BB^T + CC^T + DD^T &= 4nI_n. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Then the following array (further on called the *Williamson array*)

$$\begin{pmatrix} A & B & C & D \\ -B & A & D & -C \\ -C & -D & A & B \\ -D & C & -B & A \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

is a skew symmetric Hadamard matrix of Williamson type of order $4n$. Note that the four matrices satisfying the conditions (2) are called *Williamson type skew symmetric matrices* of order n .

An example of the skew symmetric Hadamard matrices of Williamson type of order 12 is given below.

Set the first rows of the Williamson type skew symmetric matrices of order 3 as $A = (+ - +)$, $B = C = (+ - -)$, $D = (+ + +)$ [4]. Substituting these matrices into the Williamson array (3) will give a skew symmetric Hadamard matrix of the Williamson type of order 12.

3 Block-Cyclic Skew Hadamard Matrices of Williamson Type

In this section we will consider not just block Hadamard matrices as in the previous section, but block-cyclic matrices, i.e. Hadamard matrices determined by their first block-row. Below we will show that if there exist skew Williamson type cyclic symmetric matrices of order n then there exists a block-cyclic (block-symmetric) skew Hadamard matrix of order $4n$ where the blocks of order 4 are themselves skew symmetric Hadamard matrices.

Let H be a Williamson type skew symmetric Hadamard matrix [3, 4] of order $4n$ of the form (3), where A, B, C, D are cyclic skew symmetric Williamson type matrices of order n , and consequently can be represented as follows

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} a_i U^i, & B &= \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} b_i U^i, \\ C &= \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} c_i U^i, & D &= \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} d_i U^i, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where U is a cyclic matrix of order n with first row $(0, 1, \dots, 0)$, $U^0 = U^n = I_n$ is an identity matrix of order n , and $U^{n+i} = U^i$, $a_i = -a_{n-i}$, $b_i = b_{n-i}$, $c_i = c_{n-i}$, $d_i = d_{n-i}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n-1$.

One can show that the matrix H_{4n} [6] can be represented in the following form

$$H_{4n} = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} P_i \otimes U^i, \quad (5)$$

where

$$P_i = \begin{pmatrix} a_i & b_i & c_i & d_i \\ -b_i & a_i & d_i & -c_i \\ -c_i & -d_i & a_i & b_i \\ -d_i & c_i & -b_i & a_i \end{pmatrix},$$

and $a_i, b_i, c_i, d_i = \pm 1$, $i = 0, 1, \dots, n-1$, are skew symmetric Hadamard matrices of Williamson type. Hadamard matrices of the form (5) are called the *skew symmetric block-cyclic Hadamard matrices*.

Note that there are only eight 4×4 Williamson type skew-symmetric Hadamard matrices and thus can be used in the construction of a block cyclic skew-symmetric Hadamard matrix of Williamson type. The first rows of these matrices are $P_0 = (+ + + +)$, $P_1 = (+ + + -)$, $P_2 = (+ + - +)$, $P_3 = (+ + - -)$, $P_4 = (+ - + +)$, $P_5 = (+ - + -)$, $P_6 = (+ - - +)$, and $P_7 = (+ - - -)$.

It is not difficult to show that the skew symmetric block-cyclic Hadamard matrices of Williamson type of

order 12 have the following form

$$H_{12} = P_0 \otimes I_3 - P_1 \otimes U + P_6 \otimes U^2. \quad (6)$$

4 Fast Transform Algorithms for Block-Cyclic Skew Hadamard Matrices of Williamson Type

In practice, the problem is to compute efficiently the coefficients of transforms $Y_i = P_i X$, where P_i , $i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 7$ given above and $X = (x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3)^T$ and $Y_i = (y_0^i, y_1^i, y_2^i, y_3^i)^T$, are input and output vectors, respectively. Let us denote $r_1 = x_1 + x_2 + x_3$, $r_2 = r_1 - x_0$. Then, directly from P_i , we see that the following relations hold

$$\begin{aligned} y_0^0 &= r_1 + x_0, & y_0^1 &= r_2 - 2x_3, \\ y_0^2 &= r_2 - 2x_1, & y_0^3 &= r_2 - 2x_2; \\ y_1^0 &= y_0^0 - 2x_3, & y_1^1 &= -y_0^0 + 2x_1, \\ y_1^2 &= r_2, & y_1^3 &= y_0^0 - 2x_2; \\ y_2^0 &= y_1^3 = y_0^0 - 2x_2, & y_2^1 &= r_2, \\ y_2^2 &= -y_1^1 = y_0^0 - 2x_1, & y_2^3 &= -y_0^0 = 2x_3 - y_0^0; \\ y_3^0 &= -y_0^2, & y_3^1 &= y_0^3, \\ y_3^2 &= y_0^0, & y_3^3 &= -y_0^1; \\ y_4^0 &= y_2^2 = -y_1^1 = & y_4^1 &= y_0^1 = y_0^0 - 2x_3, \\ &= y_0^0 - 2x_1, & & \\ y_4^2 &= -y_1^3 = -y_2^0 = & y_4^3 &= y_1^2 = y_2^1 = r_2; \\ &= y_0^2 - 2x_3, & & \\ y_5^0 &= -y_0^1, & y_5^1 &= -y_0^2, \\ y_5^2 &= y_0^1, & y_5^3 &= y_0^0; \\ y_6^0 &= -y_0^1, & y_6^1 &= y_0^0, \\ y_6^2 &= -y_0^3, & y_6^3 &= y_0^2; \\ y_7^0 &= -r_2, & y_7^1 &= y_1^3 = y_2^0 = y_0^0 - 2x_2, \\ y_7^2 &= y_0^1 = -y_2^3 & y_7^3 &= -y_1^1 = y_2^2 \\ &= y_0^0 - 2x_3, & & = y_0^4 = y_0^0 - 2x_1. \end{aligned}$$

Analysis of the above 4-point transforms shows that if we use them separately we need to implement 7 additions/subtractions and 3 shift operations. However, using them together requires less operations. For example, the combined transformation P_0 and P_1 of vector X requires only 10 addition/subtraction operations and 3 shift operations.

Now we will evaluate the complexity of the block-cyclic skew-symmetric Hadamard transform. Let k be the number of various blocks in the first block-row of the matrix H_{4n} and let k_i be the number of repetition of the i -th pair of blocks, $i = 1, 2, \dots, k_i$. Then the Williamson type block-cyclic skew-symmetric Hadamard transform requires only $3n$ one-bit shift operations and

$$C(H_{4n}) = n(4 + 3k) + 2(n-1)(2n + t - \sum_{i=1}^t k_i) \quad (7)$$

additions and subtractions. For example, a 20-point transform requires only 130 additions and subtractions and 15 one-bit shift operations.

The first block-rows of block-cyclic skew-symmetric Hadamard matrices of Williamson type of order $4n$ are given below

$$\begin{aligned}
n = 3 : & P_0, & -P_1, & P_6; \\
n = 5 : & P_0, & -P_0, & -P_1, & P_6, & P_7; \\
n = 7 : & P_0, & -P_0, & -P_1, & -P_2, & P_5, & P_6, \\
& & & & & & P_7; \\
n = 9 : & P_0, & -P_3, & -P_1, & -P_2, & P_2, & -P_5, \\
& & & & & P_5, & P_6, & P_4; \\
n = 11 : & P_0, & -P_3, & -P_0, & -P_3, & -P_1, & P_1, \\
& -P_6, & P_6, & P_4, & P_7, & P_4; \\
n = 13 : & P_0, & -P_3, & -P_5, & -P_5, & -P_6, & P_7, \\
& -P_7, & P_0, & -P_0, & P_1, & P_2, & P_2, \\
& & & & & & P_4; \\
n = 15 : & P_0, & -P_3, & -P_6, & -P_1, & -P_1, & -P_7, \\
& P_2, & -P_2, & P_5, & -P_5, & P_0, & P_6, \\
& & & & & P_6, & P_1, & P_4; \\
n = 17 : & P_0, & -P_6, & -P_0, & -P_1, & -P_0, & -P_7, \\
& P_7, & -P_3, & -P_4, & P_3, & P_5, & -P_0, \\
& & P_0, & P_7, & P_6, & P_7, & P_1; \\
n = 19 : & P_0, & -Q_4, & P_5, & -P_5, & -P_4, & -P_5, \\
& -P_4, & -P_7, & P_4, & P_7, & -P_0, & -P_3, \\
& P_0, & P_3, & P_2, & P_3, & P_2, & -P_2, \\
& & & & & & P_3; \\
n = 21 : & P_0, & -P_6, & -P_5, & -P_2, & -P_0, & -P_5, \\
& P_6, & -P_4, & -P_4, & P_1, & -P_1, & -P_1, \\
& -P_6, & P_3, & P_3, & -P_1, & P_2, & P_7, \\
& & & & & P_5, & P_2, & P_1; \\
n = 23 : & P_0, & -P_6, & -P_0, & -P_0, & -P_4, & -P_3, \\
& -P_0, & -P_6, & P_2, & P_1, & -P_4, & P_4, \\
& -P_3, & P_3, & -P_6, & -P_5, & P_1, & P_7, \\
& & P_4, & P_3, & P_7, & P_7, & P_1; \\
n = 25 : & P_0, & P_3, & -P_0, & -P_5, & -P_6, & -P_5, \\
& -P_5, & P_4, & -P_6, & P_5, & -P_7, & -P_4, \\
& -P_0, & P_7, & P_3, & P_0, & -P_2, & P_1, \\
& -P_3, & P_2, & P_2, & P_1, & P_2, & P_7, \\
& & & & & & -P_4;
\end{aligned}$$

Let us show an example of block-cyclic skew symmetric Hadamard matrices of Williamson type of order 12 having form (6). An input vector F_{12} is represented as $F_{12}^T = (X_0, X_1, X_2)^T$, where

$$\begin{aligned}
X_0^T &= (f_0, f_1, f_2, f_3), \\
X_1^T &= (f_4, f_5, f_6, f_7), \\
X_2^T &= (f_8, f_9, f_{10}, f_{11}).
\end{aligned}$$

The 12-point skew Hadamard transform can be represented by

$$H_{12}F_{12} = Y_0 + Y_1 + Y_2,$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
Y_0^T &= (X_0^T P_0^T, & -X_0^T P_1^T, & X_0^T P_6^T), \\
Y_1^T &= (X_1^T P_6^T, & X_1^T P_0^T, & -X_1^T P_1^T), \\
Y_2^T &= (-X_2^T P_1^T, & X_2^T P_6^T, & X_0^T P_0^T).
\end{aligned}$$

It is not difficult to see that 10 additions/subtractions and 3 shift operations are needed to compute each of the vectors $Y_i, i = 0, 1, 2$. Hence 12-point skew Hadamard transform requires only 54 additions/subtractions and 9 one bit shift operations.

5 Fast Transform Algorithms for Block-Cyclic Block-Symmetric Hadamard Matrices of Williamson Type

In [6] it was shown that if there exist Williamson type cyclic and symmetric matrices of order n then there exists a block-cyclic block-symmetric Hadamard matrix of order $4n$, where blocks of order 4 are themselves Hadamard matrices.

Let H_{4n} be a Williamson type Hadamard matrix of order $4n$, i.e.

$$H_{4n} = \begin{pmatrix} A & B & C & D \\ -B & A & -D & C \\ -C & D & A & -B \\ -D & -C & B & A \end{pmatrix},$$

where A, B, C, D are cyclic and symmetric Williamson type matrices of order n , and, consequently, can be represented by (4), and for all $i = 1, 2, \dots, n-1$ we have $a_i = a_{n-i}, b_i = b_{n-i}, c_i = c_{n-i}, d_i = d_{n-i}$.

One can show that the matrix H_{4n} can be represented in the following form of block-cyclic Hadamard matrices [3]

$$H_{4n} = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} Q_i \otimes U^i, \quad (8)$$

where

$$Q_i = \begin{pmatrix} a_i & b_i & c_i & d_i \\ -b_i & a_i & -d_i & c_i \\ -c_i & d_i & a_i & -b_i \\ -d_i & -c_i & b_i & a_i \end{pmatrix},$$

are Hadamard matrices of Williamson type when $a_i, b_i, c_i, d_i = \pm 1$, for all $i = 0, 1, \dots, n-1$.

Thus the following cyclic symmetric matrices of order 3 with first rows $(+ + +), (+ - -), (+ - -), (+ - -)$ are Williamson's type matrices.

Introduce the Williamson type Hadamard matrices of orders 4 which will be used to construct block-cyclic and block-symmetric Hadamard matrices of Williamson type of order $4n$. The first rows of these matrices are $Q_0 = (+ + + +), Q_1 = (+ + + -), Q_2 = (+ + - +), Q_3 = (+ - + +), Q_4 = (+ - - -)$.

Below the first block-rows of block-cyclic and block-symmetric Hadamard matrices of Williamson type of orders $4n, n = 3, 5, \dots, 25$ are given [3].

$$\begin{aligned}
n = 3 : & Q_0, & -Q_1; & -Q_1; \\
n = 5 : & Q_0, & -Q_2, & -Q_1; & -Q_1, & -Q_2; \\
n = 7 : & Q_0, & Q_2, & -Q_2, & Q_1, & Q_1, & -Q_2, \\
& & & & & & Q_2;
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
n = 9 : & \quad Q_0, & Q_1, & -Q_2, & Q_1, & -Q_1, & -Q_1, \\
& & & & Q_1, & -Q_2, & Q_1; \\
n = 11 : & \quad Q_0, & -Q_4, & Q_4, & Q_1, & -Q_3, & -Q_2, \\
& & -Q_2, & -Q_3, & Q_1, & Q_4, & -Q_4 \\
n = 13 : & \quad Q_0, & Q_2, & -Q_1, & -Q_1, & Q_1, & Q_2, \\
& -Q_2; & -Q_2, & Q_2, & Q_1, & -Q_1, & -Q_1, \\
& & & & & & Q_2; \\
n = 15 : & \quad Q_0, & -Q_2, & Q_1, & -Q_1, & -Q_1, & -Q_2, \\
& -Q_1, & Q_2, & Q_2, & -Q_1, & -Q_2, & -Q_1, \\
& & & & -Q_1, & Q_1, & -Q_2 \\
n = 17 : & \quad Q_0, & -Q_2, & -Q_1, & -Q_2, & -Q_3, & -Q_3, \\
& Q_3, & Q_2, & -Q_1, & -Q_1, & Q_2, & Q_3, \\
& & -Q_3, & -Q_3, & -Q_2, & -Q_1, & -Q_2; \\
n = 19 : & \quad Q_0, & Q_2, & Q_1, & -Q_2, & -Q_1, & -Q_1, \\
& Q_1, & -Q_1, & Q_2, & -Q_1, & -Q_1, & Q_2, \\
& -Q_1, & Q_1, & -Q_1, & -Q_1, & -Q_2, & Q_1, \\
& & & & & & Q_2; \\
n = 21 : & \quad Q_0, & Q_1, & Q_1, & -Q_1, & Q_1, & -Q_2, \\
& -Q_2, & Q_2, & Q_1, & Q_2, & -Q_1, & -Q_1, \\
& Q_2, & Q_1, & Q_2, & -Q_2, & -Q_2, & Q_1, \\
& & & & -Q_1, & Q_1, & Q_1; \\
n = 23 : & \quad Q_0, & Q_2, & Q_1, & -Q_2, & Q_4, & Q_3, \\
& Q_1, & -Q_3, & Q_4, & -Q_4, & -Q_2, & -Q_4, \\
& & & & & & \\
& -Q_4, & -Q_2, & -Q_4, & Q_4, & -Q_3, & Q_1, \\
& & Q_3, & Q_4, & -Q_2, & Q_1, & Q_2; \\
n = 25 : & \quad Q_0, & -Q_1, & -Q_2, & -Q_2, & -Q_1, & -Q_2, \\
& Q_2, & -Q_2, & Q_1, & Q_1, & -Q_1, & -Q_1, \\
& Q_2, & Q_2, & -Q_1, & -Q_1, & Q_1, & Q_1, \\
& -Q_2, & Q_2, & -Q_2, & -Q_1, & -Q_2, & -Q_2, \\
& & & & & & -Q_1.
\end{aligned}$$

Recall that $r_1 = x_1 + x_2 + x_3$ and $r_2 = r_1 - x_0$. Then, as in Section 4, by using matrices Q_i , $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$ we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
y_0^0 &= r_1 + x_0, & y_1^0 &= r_2 - 2x_2, \\
y_0^2 &= r_2 - 2x_3, & y_0^3 &= r_2 - 2x_1; \\
y_1^0 &= y_0^0 - 2x_3, & y_1^1 &= r_2, \\
y_1^2 &= y_0^3 - 2x_3, & y_1^3 &= y_0^0 - 2x_1; \\
y_2^0 &= y_0^0 - 2x_2, & y_2^1 &= y_0^2 - 2x_2, \\
y_2^2 &= y_0^0 - 2x_3, & y_2^3 &= r_2; \\
y_3^0 &= y_0^0 - 2x_1, & y_3^1 &= y_0^0 - 2x_2, \\
y_3^2 &= r_2, & y_3^3 &= y_0^3 - 2x_2; \\
y_4^0 &= -r_2, & y_4^1 &= y_0^0 - 2x_3, \\
y_3^0 &= y_0^0 - 2x_1, & y_3^3 &= y_0^0 - 2x_2;
\end{aligned}$$

where $(x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3)^T$ and $(y_0^i, y_1^i, y_2^i, y_3^i)$ are input and output vectors, respectively.

Analysis of given above 4-point transforms shows that if we use them separately we must implement 7 additions/subtractions and 3 shift operations, whereas their combination requires less operations.

Note that in this case the complexity of transform has the same form as in (7).

In the table below we show the necessary number of operations for given Hadamard transforms.

The columns of the Table give: Orders of symmetric (skew-symmetric) and cyclic Williamson matrices; Corresponding orders of Hadamard matrices; Number of addition and subtraction for block-cyclic block-symmetric Hadamard transform; Number of operation of the above transform with shifts; Number of addition and subtraction for block-cyclic skew symmetric Hadamard transform; Number of operations of the above transform with shifts; and Number of shifts.

n	$4n$	Symm. BC HT	Symm. BC HT with sh.	Skew symm. BC HT	Skew symm. with sh.	Num. of shifts
3	12	60	54	60	54	9
5	20	160	145	140	130	15
7	28	268	247	252	238	21
9	36	400	373	396	362	27
11	44	704	629	572	530	33
13	52	760	721	780	730	39
15	60	912	867	1020	962	45
17	68	1236	1168	1292	1226	51
19	76	1158	1219	1596	1541	57
21	84	1576	1393	1932	1632	63
23	92	2442	2329	2300	2210	69
25	100	2080	2005	2700	2602	75

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